

PROGRAMME – OPEN SCIENCE FORUM

Wednesday 14 Nov 2018

9:30 – 10:15 **TALK - Myths and Realities around Open Access**

Room – Learning Hub 2.02 (2nd floor)

Who – Jonathan England

The idea is to break some of the myths around OA (e.g. OA is a journal, OA is only possible the gold way) by presenting the 'Green' (self-archiving) and 'gold' (paying Article Processing Charges) routes and encourage researchers to always self-archive their publications.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1189190>

Speaker - Jonathan England

OpenAIRE National Open Access Representative and part of the University of Luxembourg Library team, my role is to promote Open Science practices within all research institutions in Luxembourg. I am also the main organiser of the Open Science Forum

10:30 – 12:00 **TALK - Open Licenses and Copyright 101**

Room – Learning Hub 2.02 (2nd floor)

Who – Gwen Franck

Open Licenses are essential to make Open Science work. Why is traditional copyright often an impediment for Open Science, and how can open licenses 'fix' this? What are the different licenses, how do they work, how can you apply them yourself and how can you find and reuse openly licensed materials? In this hands-on talk, we learn about the most common open licenses, in particular Creative Commons licenses, and we conduct some practical exercises in order to learn to understand and use them correctly.

Speaker - Gwen Franck

Consultant | Facilitator | All things Open

I care about facilitating access to knowledge. Only when information is accessible for everybody, its full potential can be known and used. I believe that only this way we can aim for a more equal and fair society - where all citizens can start from a level playing field.

Interested in the 'hands on' aspects of Open Science such open access publishing, self-archiving and open science tools. Advocate for the knowledge and cultural commons and open licensing. Open business model enthusiast. Interested in community engagement and policy making. Experienced workshop facilitator, event organiser, social media manager, public speaker and collaborator on several international reports. Large international network.

Available for short-term assignments such as workshop organisation, community management and reporting.

Open Access Programme Coordinator for EIFL (working on FOSTER, PASTEUR4OA and OpenAIRE projects). Other activities include: former project lead for the OpenAIRE FP7 Post Grant Open Access project on behalf of LIBER. Former Regional Coordinator Europe for Creative Commons. Co-founder of Open Access Belgium on behalf of Ghent University Library.

Board member of Open Knowledge Belgium and team lead for Creative Commons Belgium.

ORCID ID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-9719-0570>

10:30 – 12:00 **WORKSHOP - ORBilu training**

Room – Computer Training Room -2.01 (floor minus 2)

Who – Jean-Marie Carlig

REGISTRATION RECOMMENDED - 23 computers

Only open/relevant to members of the University of Luxembourg

ORBilu is the repository of the University of Luxembourg

<http://orbilu.uni.lu/>

Speaker - Jean-Marie Carlig

University of Luxembourg Library - ORBilu

12:15 – 12:45 **TALK - Persistent Identifiers**

Room – Computer Training Room -2.01 (floor minus 2)

Who – Beth Park

Some of your work keeps getting confused with another person with the same name? Some of your work does not get referenced properly because of name variants? Learn also about the importance of cross-referencing and attaching persistent identifiers to your work to increase visibility.

Speaker - Beth Park

University of Luxembourg Library

ORBilu repository manager

12:30 – 13:30 **TALK - Research Data Management: a taster**

Room – Learning Hub 2.02 (2nd floor)

Who – Gwen Franck

Attend this session if you do not have time to attend the one-day Research Data Management workshops

Managing your research data is essential when conducting scientific research. But if you've never done it before, or if you work in a field where Research Data Management (RDM) is not a hot topic, it can be a very daunting subject. In this session, we'll guide you through the basics of Research Data Management: how do you start, what is a data management plan, what do you have to pay attention to, where can you find relevant information and how can the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) help you to be as efficient at RDM as possible.

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ORCID ID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-9719-0570>

12:45 – 13:45 **WORKSHOP - ORCiD Claimathon**

Room – Computer Training Room -2.01 (floor minus 2)

Who – Beth Park

ORCID provides a persistent digital identifier that distinguishes you from every other researcher and, through integration in key research workflows such as manuscript and grant submission, supports automated linkages between you and your professional activities ensuring that your work is recognized.

In this 'Claimathon', come and learn about ORCID, create your own unique ID and link it to other services so all your research inputs get automatically added to your profile! Every researcher should have one so come and claim yours!

<https://orcid.org/>

14:00 – 15:15 **MOVIE - 'Paywall: The Business of Scholarship'**

Room – Learning Hub 2.02 (2nd floor)

Who – film screening

TRAILER: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iR08YI4_vQ4

'Paywall: The Business of Scholarship' is a documentary which focuses on the need for open access to research and science, questions the rationale behind the \$25.2 billion a year that flows into for-profit academic publishers, examines the 35-40% profit margin associated with the top academic publisher Elsevier and looks at how that profit margin is often greater than some of the most profitable tech companies like Apple, Facebook and Google.

14:00 – 15:00 **TALK - Getting ready for the blind date - Fundamentals of IP management in Horizon2020**

Room – Meeting Room -2.01 (Floor minus 2)

Who – Onur Emul

Management of intellectual property (IP) in Horizon 2020 projects can be quite challenging. But life itself is quite challenging, isn't it? Think that you are on a blind-date with your future girl/boy friend. How would you act, what would you say or what would you hide about yourself and what would you order for dinner? Do not forget, IP management in H2020 with your future consortium partners is no different. Come and see.

Speaker - Onur Emul

Intellectual Property Institute Luxembourg - European IPR Helpdesk - Intellectual Property Advisor

Onur Emul is an Intellectual Property (IP) Advisor with more than ten years of experience in this field, with chemical engineering background. After working as a Patent and Trademark Attorney for several years, he served as an expert for the Enterprise Europe Network, a project funded by the European Commission, dealing with IP issues in technology transfer and innovation management processes along with project development and communication activities. Onur acted also as the European IPR Helpdesk Ambassador in Turkey, and was a registered IP Court Expert in Criminal and Civil Law cases. He is now working for the European Commission's European IPR Helpdesk, headquartered in Luxembourg, in charge of publications and stakeholder management. He is also a EuKTS Associate on knowledge transfer.

15:30 – 17:00 **DEBATE - Academic publishing**

Room – Learning Hub 2.02 (2nd floor)

Who – chair: Sean Sapcariu

Are publishing companies really on your side? Do you agree on how costly it is to publish digital content? Do you even still need to publish in journals to share your work? Come and share your thoughts and debate about the current situation and what the future of academic publishing could look like.

Chair - Sean Sapcariu

FNR - Programme Manager

Thursday 15 Nov 2018

9:30 – 17:30 **WORKSHOP - Introduction to Humanities Research Data Management**

Room – Learning Hub 1.01 (first floor)

Who – Ulrike Wuttke & Jochen Klar

Reusable, machine-readable data are one pillar of Open Science (Open Scholarship). Serving this data reuse aspect requires from researchers to carefully document their methods and to take good care of their research data. Due to this paradigm shift, for Humanities and Heritage researchers, activities and issues around planning, organizing, storing, and sharing data and other research results and products play an increasing role. Therefore, during two workshop sessions Ulrike Wuttke and Jochen Klar will dive with the participants into a number of topics, technologies, and methods that are connected with Humanities Research Data Management. The participants will acquire knowledge and skills that will enable them to draft their own executable research data management plan that will support the production of reusable, machine-readable data, a key prerequisite for conducting effective and sustainable projects. Topics that will be covered are theoretical reflections on the role of data within humanities research and cultural heritage studies, opportunities and challenges of eHumanities and eResearch, implementing the FAIR principles and relevant standards, and basics of Data Management Planning.

Learning outcomes: Participants of this workshop will gain an overview about issues related to Humanities Research Data Management and learn about relevant tools and information resources. Through a hands-on session, the participants will be especially equipped and skilled to draft the nucleus of their own Research Data Management Plan.

Structure of the workshop: The workshop will consist of two sessions. In the **morning session**, the basics of Humanities Research Data Management will be discussed with the participants using examples from various humanities backgrounds and projects. The **afternoon session** will be dedicated to hands-on data management planning using the data management planning tool RDMO. This supervised practical exercise will offer the participants the opportunity to learn by doing. Participants are encouraged to discuss data management issues related to their own projects (or project ideas) ideas and to contact the trainers beforehand.

Audience: The workshop sessions are aimed at Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage researchers and practitioners with who wish to learn how to enable good Research Data Management and the sharing and reuse of data from a humanities point of view. No special previous knowledge or programming skills are required.

TRAINERS

Ulrike Wuttke (Doctor of Literature, Universiteit Gent 2012, wuttke@fh-potsdam.de) is a medievalist and textual scholar by training. She contributes to projects and networks in digital preservation and digital arts and humanities via groups such as the Working Group Data Centres of the Verband Digital Humanities im deutschsprachigen Raum (deputy convenor). Her professional activities focus on training and personal counselling on data management, open science and Digital Humanities as well as public relations, communication and outreach. She joined the PARTHENOS project and FH Potsdam in April 2017. She leads task 7.2 (Implementation of the Training plan) of the H2020 project PARTHENOS. She coordinates the further development of its online training platform, the PARTHENOS Training Suite, and the PARTHENOS eHumanities and eHeritage Webinar Series.

Jochen Klar (PhD in numerical cosmology, University of Potsdam 2012, jklar@aip.de) works in the area of data management and eScience at the Leibniz Institute for Astrophysics Potsdam (AIP) and takes part in various data related projects, both in astrophysics as well as in interdisciplinary contexts. He was involved in the development of several astronomical data portals (e.g. RAVE, APPLAUSE, CosmoSim, GREGOR). For the DFG projects RADIESCHEN and DFG-VRE, he investigated the sustainability and the organizational structure of data management and virtual research environments in Germany. He is the main developer of the Daiquiri framework for the publication of astronomical databases and of the RDM-planning tool RDMO (Research Data Management Organiser).

Links:

PARTHENOS Main Site: <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/>

PARTHENOS Training Suite: <http://training.parthenos-project.eu/>

RDMO Main Site: <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/en/>

9:30 – 17:00 **WORKSHOP - Good data management and open research principles (all research fields)**

Room – Meeting Room -2.01 (Floor minus 2)

Who – S. Venkataraman

The Research Data Management workshops on Wednesday and Thursday are identical, please register to only one.

This one-day workshop will introduce the concepts of research data management (RDM), open research and data management plans (DMPs). The workshop will teach researchers and support staff successful methods for engaging in, and be shown the benefits of, open data sharing and will enable them to dispel common fears. Practical sessions will offer the opportunity to examine different approaches and discuss what might be adapted for the Luxembourg context. Overall, the workshop will provide practical advice to better understand RDM best practice and give the fundamentals to disseminate this knowledge. Please note that timings are approximate.

TRAINER - Shanmugasundaram Venkataraman (Venkat)

Research Data Specialist and Training Lead, Digital Curation Centre, UK

After spending my undergraduate and postgraduate years learning biochemistry in the field of chromatin, leading to a PhD, I switched to other major interests in biology for my early career - developmental biology and biomedical imaging. I joined the eMouseAtlas Project (formerly the Edinburgh Mouse Atlas Project, an open source, open access project) at a time when bioinformatics and the use of computers in labs was still very limited and this gave me an opportunity to explore many new avenues. I was primarily involved in imaging of mouse embryos and curation of image data into spatial atlases created by eMouseAtlas. This involved many novel techniques and the use of bespoke software as well as commercial methods. In terms of research data management practises, we created our own pipelines and infrastructure, in large part due to a lack of outside guidance and funder requirements, and since we were generating and handling large amounts of data, this was essential. However, our RDM practices were mostly in line with current RDM good practice guidelines

10:45 – 12:45 **WORKSHOP - Zotero reference manager**

Room – Computer Training Room -2.01 (floor minus 2)

Who – Simon Audigier

To collect and save interesting bibliographic references is always time consuming.

To cite in the correct style is complex and detailed.

Bibliographic managers make organising, storing and citing references easier.

Zotero is a free and open-source reference management software to manage bibliographic data and related research materials.

This tool enables you to:

- Collect your references from databases, websites, catalogues...
- Organise them by folders and tags
- Annotate your citations
- Cite in the correct style directly in your document
- Share your references with fellow researchers

Trainer - Simon Audigier

University of Luxembourg Library

14:15 – 15:45 **WORKSHOP - The Scientific Scavenger Hunt: Improve your discovery skills**

Room – Learning Hub 2.02 (2nd floor)

Who – Christopher Kittel

The open science revolution has dramatically increased the accessibility of scientific knowledge. But what about discoverability? Discovery is in many ways the departure point of research; whether you are starting out in your PhD, initiating a research project or venturing into a different discipline: in many cases, you want to get an overview of an unknown field of research and the most relevant projects therein. The quality of this overview often decides whether research gets reused or duplicated, whether collaborations are formed or such opportunities are missed. However, with 2.5 million papers published every year, and thousands of research projects launched every day, discovery becomes increasingly difficult. Traditional approaches involving search engines providing long, unstructured lists of scientific outputs are not sufficient. We can also see this reflected in the numbers: the vast majority of datasets are not reused, and even in application-oriented disciplines such as medicine, only a minority of results ever gets transferred to practice. But not to worry, open science is here to help: new and innovative tools for exploring scientific knowledge are bridging the gap between accessibility and discoverability. In this workshop, you will learn to improve your discovery skills with two open science tools enabling visual discovery: Open Knowledge Maps (<https://openknowledgemaps.org/search>), which provides knowledge maps of research topics in any discipline, and VIPER (<https://openknowledgemaps.org/viper>), which builds on the EOSC via OpenAIRE to enable visual discovery of research projects. You will learn how to get an overview of a scientific field, to identify relevant concepts and to separate relevant from irrelevant content with respect to your information need. This training will be given in the form of an innovative, hands-on format: the Scientific Scavenger Hunt. The Scientific Scavenger Hunt is a fun and fast-paced mix between a pub quiz and a virtual scavenger hunt. In groups, participants try and complete tasks on knowledge maps within a given time limit. They follow hints on knowledge maps that lead you to the correct answer.

On the way, they learn what makes a guerilla archivist and why the city of Athens is almost synonymous with insomnia in some communities. And they may even win a prize in the end! We have already conducted this workshop around the world. More than a 1000 participants have participated in this fun, hands-on activity at events such as the Open Science Fair and OpenCon, and we would love to bring it to DI4R. *More information on Open Knowledge Maps: Open Knowledge Maps is based on the principles of open science: we share our source code, content and data under an open license. As a community-driven initiative, we are developing our services together with our advisors, collaboration partners and users. Currently, more than 30,000 users from all around the world leverage our openly accessible discovery tool for their research, writing and studies per month. For more information, please visit <https://openknowledgemaps.org>

Speaker - Christopher Kittel

<http://www.christopherkittel.eu/>

16:00 – 17:00 **TALK - Figshare and the FAIR Principles**

Room – Learning Hub 2.02 (2nd floor)

Who – Stephen Cawley (Figshare)

Friday 16 Nov 2018

9:15 – 9:45 **TALK - Persistent Identifiers**

Room – Computer Training Room -2.01 (floor minus 2)

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<https://orcid.org/>

9:30 – 10:45 **DEBATE - Research Evaluation**

Room – Learning Hub 2.02 (2nd floor)

Who – chair: Helena Burg

Do you agree on how research is evaluated? On how you are judged as researchers? Are journal metrics such as the Impact Factor good tools? Come and have your say and debate about research evaluation.

Chair - Helena Burg

FNR - Head of Interational Affairs

11:00 – 12:00 **TALK - Fears and Thrills of Data Sharing**

Room – Learning Hub 2.02 (2nd floor)

Who – Katrina Bramstedt

In the complex world of research there can be many things to fear: Research ethics committee review, lengthy informed consent forms, murky privacy regulations, numerous data storage tools and their security profiles, third-party data use agreements, and local and international regulatory requirements. Viewing research as a community good that should be shared in order to maximize its benefit to society, how does a researcher successfully navigate these waters and ethically share its data treasury? This session will explore this dilemma, offer navigation guidance, and ideas for data sharing that can add reward to the research experience. (This session is interactive – please bring your smartphone/e-device.)

Speaker - Katrina Bramstedt

Secretary General of the Luxembourg Agency for Research Integrity (LARI)

12:15 – 13:00 **TALK - Open Access to scholar publications : from the Berlin Declaration to Plan S**

Room – Learning Hub 2.02 (2nd floor)

Who – Marc Schiltz

On 4 September, the FNR and 10 other national research funding organisations, with the support of the European Commission (EC) and the European Research Council (ERC), have launched **cOAlition S**, a joint initiative to make full and immediate Open Access to research publications a reality by 2020. The initiative is promoted by Science Europe, the association of national research funding and research performing organisations in Europe.

Speaker - Marc Schiltz

President of Science Europe, FNR Secretary General

I hold a PhD in Physics (Crystallography) and an Executive MBA from INSEAD. I have been active in research and higher education for more than 20 years in several European countries (France, United Kingdom, Switzerland, Luxembourg) and I am a recognised scientist in my field of expertise.

Drawing on my international experience, I have developed a thorough expertise in strategic research management and organisation. Since 2011, I am heading the National Research Fund of Luxembourg. In this role, I bring a strong dedication to building a world-class research system in Luxembourg that will generate long-term societal and economic impact for the country. I have significantly contributed to enhance the quality of the Luxembourg research system and to build bridges with the private sector as well as with the international scientific community.

Since 2017, I am the president of Science Europe, the Brussels-based association of all major European public research funding and research performing organisations, representing a combined annual investment in research of around 18 bn EUR in 27 countries. I also sit on the Governing Board of the Global Research Council, which comprises the heads of research funding agencies from around the world

I am a relentless advocate of science and research and serve on a number of external boards and committees, both at the national and international level. I actively promote an open dialogue between the science community and decision-makers and conceive my role to be that of an ambassador for science as an important contributor to societal development.

I have a particularly strong commitment to support activities that promote scientific culture and raise public awareness for research and science. Thus, within Luxembourg, the FNR has achieved a leadership position in the promotion of science to the public, as the organizer of science fairs, educational programmes, and also co-producer of a popular science show on the local TV channel.

13:00 – 13:45 **TALK - FNR Open Access Policy and Open Access Fund**

Room – Learning Hub 2.02 (2nd floor)

Who – Sean Sapcarui

FNR Open Access Policy and Open Access Fund information session

13:00 – 13:45 **TALK - Personal data, pseudonymisation and anonymization: how to find your way around?**

Room – Meeting Room -2.01 (Floor minus 2)

Who – Sandrine Munoz

Get familiar with the notion of personal data and the processing of personal data with some elements about techniques of anonymisation.

Speaker - Sandrine Munoz

University of Luxembourg - Data Protection Officer

14:00 – 15:30 **DEBATE - Gender issues in Open Science and Open Innovation**

Room – Learning Hub 2.02 (2nd floor)

Who – Marcela Linková

In my combined talk and discussion, I will explore possible intersections between gender and Open Science and Open Innovation (OS/OI). Focusing on selected key aspects of OS/OI policies and practices, I will show that most analyses and policy documents related to OS/OI adopt a gender blind approach, with such an approach being more pronounced in the case of OS policies and practices than in the case of OI. I will argue that the consideration of gender issues in the development of OS/OI policies could have a positive impact on the promotion of gender equality goals and elimination of gender biases.

I will first examine what the gender issues are in selected aspects of Open Science, for instance through open access to publications and research data or the ways in which open access practices can be embedded in research evaluation/assessment procedures. Given the existing knowledge about gender differences in research publication as well as gender bias in research evaluation and assessment, it is for example pertinent to examine open peer review and altmetrics for potential relevance of gender. I will go on to consider the ways in which open innovation practices (such as crowdsourcing and citizen science) can contribute to advancing gender equality and gendered innovations. I will highlight the need to address the gender dimension on innovation processes overall, as well as the need to address diversity and gender balance in open innovation processes. In conclusion, I will formulate recommendations in selected priority areas for action addressed to different stakeholders, which I will open for discussion with the participants.

GENDERACTION project (<http://genderaction.eu/>)

Speaker - Marcela Linková

Marcela Linková PhD is a researcher at the Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences where she directs the Centre for Gender and Science. She has a doctorate in sociology from Charles University in Prague. Her research focuses on sociology of gendered organizations, research careers, governance of research and research assessment from a gender perspective. Marcela also examines the material-discursive practices through which gender equality policies and initiatives are adopted and implemented at the European and Czech country levels. She is the chair of the ERAC Standing Working Group on Gender in Research and Innovation; before she was the co-chair of the Commission's Helsinki Group on Gender in Research and Innovation. She is active in developing policy solutions for gender equality in research at the Czech and EU levels. She has served on expert and advisory bodies of the European Commission and in the Czech Republic. She publishes on gender equality in research, and in together with Mary Frank Fox and Kjersten Bunker Whittington contributed to the 4th edition of *the Handbook of Science and Technology Studies* (2017). She is an alumna of the International Visitor Leadership Programme "Women in STEM".

14:00 – 15:30 **WORKSHOP - Data anonymisation - AMNESIA workshop**

Room – Computer Training Room -2.01 (floor minus 2)

Who – Manolis Terrovitis

Amnesia is a data anonymization tool, that allows to remove identifying information from data. Amnesia not only removes direct identifiers like names, SSNs etc but also transforms secondary identifiers like birth date and zip code so that individuals cannot be identified in the data. Amnesia supports k -anonymity and km -anonymity

<https://amnesia.openaire.eu/>

Speaker - Manolis Terrovitis

Information Management Systems Institute (IMSI), "Athena" Research Center

I am an associate researcher at the [Institute for the Management of Information Systems](#) (IMIS) of the Research and Innovation Centre in Information, Communication and Knowledge Technologies "Athena". My main research interests lie in the areas of Privacy Preservation and Big Data management. I am also interested in the management of spatiotemporal data, query processing and indexing for containment queries. I am managing two related projects in IMIS: [MEDA](#), which focuses on big data management and [MoDiSENSE](#), which deals with location based social networks. In the past I have been a post doc fellow at the Department of Computer Science of the [The University of Hong Kong](#) and I have taught courses related to data management for several years in the Masters Program of the Department of Computer Science and Technology in The University of Peloponnese and in the Geoinformatics Master's program of NTUA as an Adjunct Lecturer. I received my PhD in 2007 from the National Technical University of Athens, under the supervision of Prof. Timos Sellis.

URL: <https://web.imis.athena-innovation.gr/~mter/>

15:30 – 17:30 **OPEN SCIENCE CAFÉ**

Room – Learning Hub 2.02 (2nd floor)

Besides the various topics that will be discussed during the debate sessions, the Open Science Café will be a designated **time to gather**, socialise **and discuss any topics** you may have. In small or large groups, following up a discussion or starting a new topic, it is a free time to **share your interests and/or concerns**. Discussion cards will also be provided in case you need to spark up the conversation.

Drinks and light bites will be provided.